

Supplementary materials

Boosting phylogenetic bootstrap with structural information

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Supplementary Fig. S1: Comparison of the average NiRMSD per family on the three different alignment methods. Distribution of the average NiRMSD per family of the MSAs produced by T-Coffee (blue), 3D-Coffee (sap+TMalign) (grey) and mTM-align (orange). The medians of each distribution are reported. Boxplots show the median, quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles) and whiskers extend to 1.5 times the IQR.

Supplementary Fig. S2: Agreement between input and patristic distances using alternative MSA strategies. Boxplot of the coefficient of determination (R^2) measured between the input and patristic distance matrices estimated on each dataset by ME (purple) and IMD (blue) on (A) trimmed mTAlign MSAs (B) untrimmed 3D-Coffee MSAs (C) trimmed 3D-Coffee MSAs, (D) untrimmed T-Coffee MSAs, (E) trimmed T-Coffee MSAs. Boxplots show the median, quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles) and whiskers extend to 1.5 times the IQR.

Supplementary Fig. S3: Relationship between bootstrap support values and topological similarities across tree methods using alternative MSA strategies. (A) For each dataset, the average bootstrap support value of the ME tree (y-axis) is plotted against its IMD counterpart (x-axis) and colored by the RF topological distance, with both types of trees being computed using 3D-Coffee to combine sap and TAlign pairwise structural alignments into structural MSAs. The black overlaying line is a running average RF (x-tree, y-tree, window size of 10) computed over the datasets sorted by IMD bootstrap support values. Similar analyses were carried out using (B) 3D-Coffee and ML trees, (C) T-Coffee MSAs and ME trees, (D) T-Coffee MSAs and ML trees.

Supplementary Fig. S4: Relationship between bootstrap support values and topological similarities across tree methods using alternative MSA strategies combined with trimming. (A) For each dataset the average bootstrap support value of the ME tree (y-axis) is plotted against its IMD counterpart (x-axis) and colored by the RF topological distance, with both types of trees being computed using trimmed mTM-align MSAs. The black overlaying line is a running average RF (x-tree, y-tree, window size of 10) computed over the datasets sorted by IMD bootstrap support values ($R=-0.67$). Similar analyses were carried out using alternatively **(B)** trimmed mTMalign MSAs and ML trees, **(C)** 3D-Coffee to combine sap and TMalign pairwise structural alignments into a structural MSA subsequently trimmed and ME tree, **(D)** Trimmed 3D-Coffee MSAs and ML, **(E)** trimmed T-Coffee MSAs and ME, **(F)** trimmed T-Coffee MSAs and ML.

Supplementary Fig. S5: Relationships between bootstrap support values and topological similarities on trees computed on untrimmed alignments. (A) The red line represents the fraction of branches having an IMD bootstrap support value $\geq X$ (x-axis) that occur in the ME trees (all datasets put together). The blue line indicates which fraction of the total number of IMD branches (8,813 branches in total) are represented by each red point. The trees were computed using 3D-Coffee to combine sap and TAlign pairwise structural alignments into structural MSAs. Similar analyses were carried out using alternatively (B) 3D-Coffee and ML trees, (C) T-Coffee MSAs and ME trees, (D) T-Coffee MSAs and ML trees.

Supplementary Fig. S6: Relationships between bootstrap support value and topological similarities on trees computed on trimmed alignments. **(A)** The red line represents the fraction of branches having an IMD bootstrap support value $\geq X$ (x-axis) that occur in the ME trees (all datasets put together). The blue line indicates which fraction of the total number of IMD branches (8,813 branches in total) are represented by each red point. Trees are computed using trimmed mTMalign MSAs. Similar analyses were carried out using alternatively **(B)** trimmed mTMalign MSAs and ML trees, **(C)** 3D-Coffee to combine sap and TMalign pairwise structural alignments into a structural MSA subsequently trimmed and ME tree, **(D)** Trimmed 3D-Coffee MSAs and ML, **(E)** trimmed T-Coffee MSAs and ME, **(F)** trimmed T-Coffee MSAs and ML.

Supplementary Fig. S7: Information content comparison using 3D-Coffee MSAs. (A)

Fraction of reference branches recovered on downsampled MSAs while using MSAs generated by 3D-Coffee used to combine sap and TMalign pairwise alignments. The x-axis indicates the number of columns (out of a maximum of 200) kept in MSAs downsampled from 560 different MSAs (56 datasets sampled ten times each) and the y-axis indicates the fraction of reference branches recovered for a given level of downsampling. The gray dashed line indicates the number of columns required to recover 75% of the reference branches. The envelope is the standard deviation. **(B)** Represents a similar analysis carried out using the 49 datasets and the 490 MSAs generated with mTMalign. These 49 datasets are the ones for which all AF2 structures could be retrieved. The lighter colors show the analysis carried out using the experimental structures and the darker ones show the analysis when carried out with the AF2 structures.

MSA	Tree type	Median R ² (input, patristic)	Average BS	Congruence with ML trees	Congruence with ML trees (BS>=75)	ML Shared branches (count)	BS=100 ML Shared branches (count)
mTMalign	ME	0.898	43.47	0.67	0.87	67.00% (5601)	100% (552)
	TM	0.962		0.4		39.75% (3240)	
	IMD	0.970	66.37	0.42	0.55	42.11% (3416)	83.17% (1591)
3D-Coffee	ME	0.884	44.42	0.68	0.87	67.64% (5532)	100% (608)
	IMD	0.975	66.66	0.41	0.53	41.06% (3249)	81.76% (1537)
T-Coffee	ME	0.937	42.63	0.42	0.58	41.75% (3431)	75.74% (562)
	IMD	0.982	67.80	0.21	0.25	20.93% (1643)	43.07% (851)

Supplementary Table 1: Summary statistics for trees rendered on untrimmed alignments.

Table with summary statistics on the 508 families on which all the methods produce all the bootstrap replicates.

MSA	Tree type	Median R ² (input, patristic)	Average BS	Congruence with ML trees	Congruence with ML trees (BS>=75)	BS support ML Shared branches (count)	BS=100 ML Shared branches (count)
mTMalign	ME	0.901	39.00	0.66	0.88	66.05% (5384)	100% (397)
	IMD	0.964	61.30	0.38	0.52	37.54% (2938)	82.05% (1239)
3D-Coffee	ME	0.879	41.32	0.67	0.88	66.75% (5398)	100% (467)
	IMD	0.975	63.18	0.39	0.52	38.72% (2965)	81.24% (1286)
T-Coffee	ME	0.909	40.82	0.67	0.88	67.15% (5424)	99.79% (480)
	IMD	0.982	64.03	0.38	0.51	37.65% (2866)	79.09% (1276)

Supplementary Table 2: Summary statistics for trees rendered on trimmed alignments.

Table with summary statistics on the 508 families on which all the methods produce all the bootstrap replicates.

Ref. branches	Number ref. branches	% branches	Number of trees	average relative depth	average depth
IMD80	314	37.880	55	0.350	3.170
ME80	285	34.380	55	0.360	3.070
ML80	344	41.500	55	0.360	3.260
ME80 \cap IMD80	209	25.640	54	0.350	2.980
ML80 \cap IMD80	240	30.530	52	0.350	3.040
ME80 \cap ML80	253	30.520	55	0.350	3.050
ME80 \cap ML80 \cap IMD80	196	24.940	52	0.350	2.970
Average	263	32.199	54.000	0.353	3.077

Supplementary Table 3: Descriptive statistics of the various combinations used to determine reference branches on ML Trees.

	IMD	ME	ME+IMD	ML	ML+IMD	ME+ML	ME+ML+IMD
IMD	-	2.00E-10	4.57E-05	5.97E-03	1.27E-09	2.61E-04	2.48E-03
ME	2.00E-10	-	3.87E-32	1.82E-10	1.01E-32	2.50E-11	1.49E-35
ME+IMD	4.57E-05	3.87E-32	-	8.14E-11	1.50E-05	7.72E-17	7.46E-01
ML	5.97E-03	1.82E-10	8.14E-11	-	1.54E-20	2.72E-02	5.83E-17
ML+IMD	1.27E-09	1.01E-32	1.50E-05	1.54E-20	-	1.68E-23	2.84E-08
ME+ML	2.61E-04	2.50E-11	7.72E-17	2.72E-02	1.68E-23	-	2.47E-24
ME+ML+IMD	2.48E-03	1.49E-35	7.46E-01	5.83E-17	2.84E-08	2.47E-24	-

Supplementary Table 4: Paired Wilcoxon test p-values associated with the differences between the AUC values of the approach reported in the column and the ones of the approach reported in the row for each of the families.

	Bootstrap combinations and resulting average AUC values						
Ref branches	IMD	ME	ME +IMD	ML	ML +IMD	ME+ML	ME+ML +IMD
IMD80	0.934 ± 0.08	0.773 ± 0.16	0.921 ± 0.09	0.798 ± 0.17	0.931 ± 0.08	0.792 ± 0.17	0.902 ± 0.09
ME80	0.796 ± 0.17	0.819 ± 0.16	0.848 ± 0.15	0.854 ± 0.16	0.867 ± 0.14	0.845 ± 0.16	0.861 ± 0.14
ME80∩IMD80	0.902 ± 0.12	0.838 ± 0.15	0.920 ± 0.11	0.864 ± 0.15	0.930 ± 0.10	0.858 ± 0.16	0.914 ± 0.10
ML80	0.833 ± 0.15	0.790 ± 0.16	0.862 ± 0.13	0.851 ± 0.13	0.894 ± 0.11	0.832 ± 0.15	0.875 ± 0.12
ML80∩IMD80	0.923 ± 0.10	0.816 ± 0.16	0.930 ± 0.08	0.846 ± 0.16	0.943 ± 0.07	0.837 ± 0.17	0.917 ± 0.08
ME80∩ML80	0.828 ± 0.15	0.836 ± 0.14	0.877 ± 0.11	0.882 ± 0.12	0.904 ± 0.09	0.868 ± 0.13	0.893 ± 0.09
ME80∩ML80∩IMD80	0.906 ± 0.12	0.848 ± 0.15	0.929 ± 0.10	0.871 ± 0.15	0.937 ± 0.10	0.864 ± 0.16	0.921 ± 0.10
Average	0.875	0.817	0.898	0.852	0.915	0.842	0.898

Supplementary Table 5: Discrimination capacities of the downsampled bootstrap support values estimated on ME trees. The table reports the average AUC measured on the titration family along with their standard deviation (\pm). *Ref. Branches* indicate which combination of non-downsampled bootstrap support values (as estimated on 200 columns) were used to select the reference branches as branches having a support of 80 or more among the replicates of the considered methods. *Bootstrap Combination* indicates which bootstrap replicates (estimated on 25 columns) were combined (arithmetic mean) to estimate the bootstrap support values. The average AUC values indicate the discriminative capacity of the bootstrap combination between reference and non-reference branches as estimated on the original ML trees. Readouts in bold indicate bootstrap combinations featuring IMD. The shading indicates matched pairs of columns with and without IMD information (except for the first column).

Combination method	Bootstrap combinations and resulting average AUC values			
	ME+IMD	ML+IMD	ME+ML	ME+ML+IMD
Arithmetic Mean	0.880	0.902	0.869	0.892
Geometric Mean	0.865	0.880	0.868	0.871
Minimum	0.864	0.873	0.859	0.871
Maximum	0.857	0.881	0.881	0.878

Supplementary Table 6: Comparison of the bootstrap support values combinations readouts depending on the combination protocols for ML trees (as in Table 3) using ME80∩ML80 reference branches (average values).

		Bootstrap combinations						
Ref branches		IMD	ME	ME+IMD	ML	ML+IMD	ME+ML	ME+ML+IMD
IMD80	Sensitivity	0.91	0.78	0.90	0.81	0.90	0.81	0.90
	Specificity	0.93	0.83	0.92	0.85	0.93	0.83	0.90
ME80	Sensitivity	0.82	0.84	0.82	0.89	0.84	0.87	0.84
	Specificity	0.85	0.86	0.91	0.86	0.92	0.87	0.91
ME80∩IMD80	Sensitivity	0.89	0.85	0.93	0.91	0.94	0.89	0.94
	Specificity	0.92	0.87	0.91	0.86	0.93	0.87	0.91
ML80	Sensitivity	0.82	0.82	0.84	0.82	0.87	0.82	0.86
	Specificity	0.88	0.81	0.88	0.88	0.90	0.86	0.87
ML80∩IMD80	Sensitivity	0.90	0.81	0.89	0.86	0.93	0.84	0.91
	Specificity	0.93	0.86	0.92	0.87	0.92	0.87	0.90
ME80∩ML80	Sensitivity	0.84	0.82	0.87	0.89	0.90	0.88	0.88
	Specificity	0.87	0.89	0.89	0.88	0.91	0.88	0.90
ME80∩ML80∩IMD80	Sensitivity	0.91	0.86	0.94	0.92	0.95	0.90	0.95
	Specificity	0.91	0.87	0.92	0.85	0.92	0.87	0.91
Average	Sensitivity	0.87	0.83	0.88	0.87	0.90	0.86	0.90
	Specificity	0.90	0.85	0.91	0.86	0.92	0.86	0.90

Supplementary Table 7: Sensitivity and specificity levels achieved at optimal separation between reference and non-reference branches, as estimated by the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). Matched pairs of columns have similar shadings. Matched pairs of cells corresponding to reference determined without structural information (ME80, ML80, and ME80∩ML80 reference branches) are highlighted in yellow if they correspond to a situation where the addition of IMD information resulted in a degradation of performances, in blue if no variation occurred and in green otherwise.

	IMD +/- SD		ME +/- SD		ME+IMD +/-SD		ML +/-SD		ML+IMD +/- SD		ME+ML +/-SD		ME+ML+IMD +/- SD	
IMD80	27	22	22	21	27	15	29	25	31	18	24	19	27	16
ME80	40	31	23	20	33	17	29	20	36	16	26	18	32	16
ME80∩IMD80	50	28	30	21	39	16	34	24	41	15	32	19	37	15
ML80	33	29	19	19	29	18	27	23	30	18	24	20	28	17
ML80∩IMD80	44	28	28	22	36	17	33	24	38	18	30	21	34	17
ME80∩ML80	42	31	27	21	34	17	34	23	38	18	29	18	35	16
ME80∩ML80∩IMD80	52	28	30	21	40	16	35	24	43	16	32	20	38	16
Average	41	28	26	21	34	17	32	23	37	17	28	19	33	16

Supplementary Table 8: Bootstrap support value thresholds required to achieve optimal separation as estimated by the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), reported along with their standard deviations (grayed columns). The bootstrap support values are rounded to their nearest integer and correspond to the specificities and sensitivities reported in Supplementary Table 7.